

Reshaping Identities. How the Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation Navigates the Digital Age Making Sense of Its Heritage.

E. Missaggia¹

¹University Ca' Foscari of Venice, Venice School of Management, Italy

Abstract

The paper examines how the identity of a cultural institution is deeply connected with its territory and how both must adapt to contemporary socio-economic challenges. In this context, digital innovation emerges as a strategic lever for institutional transformation, reshaping identities, expanding outreach, and developing new models of engagement and accessibility. The case study of Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation, located in Venice, exemplifies how the ongoing digital transformation process is reshaping the institution's identity, generating both internal and external impacts. Historically, Palazzo Giustinian Lolin was a cultural hub thanks to its central location and the work of the Levi couple, who transformed their residence into a salon for music, art, and culture. After their death, it became the seat of the Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation, hosting events and research activities. Today, in a context of mass tourism and globalization, the Foundation seeks to maintain its territorial connection while pursuing new forms of cultural accessibility through the implementation of the LeviDigiLab, its digitization laboratory. The findings indicate that the digitization process has the potential to reshape the Foundation's identity, acting as a driver of its cultural and social regeneration. While this case reflects how one institution responds to its unique local conditions, further research is required to assess how such dynamics manifest in other urban contexts.

CCS Concepts

· Applied computing → Computers in other domains → Digital Libraries and archives.

1. Objectives of research

In the heart of Venice, amidst winding alleys and historic buildings, narratives of cultural identity are continuously evolving in response to contemporary needs. The city's cultural institutions, custodians of centuries-old heritage, now face unprecedented challenges: mass tourism, globalization [SSP18; Rus02], and digital innovation are redefining their roles and their relationship with the local cultural ecosystem. To navigate these rapid changes, cultural institutions are called to demonstrate a strong level of maturity and the ability to adapt to the new demands of the sector. Central to this is the concept of organizational identity. Existing literature suggests that the identity of an organization is defined by its central, distinctive, and durable attributes [AW85; Whe06]. While this theoretical proposition allows institutions to differentiate themselves within their sector, it also requires them to continuously evolve in response to social transformations, following what is known as a 'adaptive instability' process [CH09]. This is particularly relevant in the case of cultural organizations forced to abide by digital transformation: such a shift destabilizes the very material foundations of conservation and safeguarding practices. Therefore, we wonder how digital transformation impacts the identity of cultural organization. In this ever-evolving cultural landscape, digital innovation is emerging as a strategic lever capable of repositioning cultural institutions within the marketplace, reconstructing new organizational identities that align with contemporary demands.

This paper examines the deep interconnection between cultural institutions and their territory, focusing on how both must adapt to contemporary challenges such as the implementation of digital practices. In academic discourses, heritage is increasingly associated with the construction of a shared and localized identity

[Con21], resulting from a dynamic and continuous process of reinterpretation [Lüh06]. Its vitality lies in its use and the active participation of the communities that inherit it, making heritage a tool for the construction of collective identity [Har13]. In this evolving paradigm, cultural institutions act as essential mediators in this process, no longer merely as custodians of heritage but as active agents in its interpretation and dissemination [GAT00]. In a context such as Venice, where overtourism and globalization have radically transformed the city's social, economic and cultural fabric [RG21; SSP18; Rus02], the role of institutions becomes even more crucial. Furthermore, in this scenario, digitization emerges as a strategic lever for redefining the role of cultural institutions and strengthening their connection to their local context. The paradigm of Digital Humanities provides innovative tools for reinterpreting heritage in an inclusive and participatory manner, overcoming the physical limitations of exhibition spaces and making heritage accessible to broader audiences [KKA07], while contributing to the diversification of institution's economic models [Gia12].

As already described, the research focuses on the Venetian territory, an ecosystem distinguished by a dense network of cultural institutions, creating an environment in which culture and economy must coexist in a delicate equilibrium [RG21]. Within this dynamic landscape, cultural institutions are compelled to engage in a continuous process of self-reassessment to meet the evolving needs of both local and international audiences. Among the numerous institutions operating within the city, the Ugo and Olga Foundation presents a particularly compelling case study for analysing the impact of digitization on cultural institutions. Historically, the Levi Foundation has embodied a well-defined cultural mission, deeply intertwined with the city's social and intellectual fabric. However, more recently, the evolving dynamics of mass tourism, globalization, and demographic shifts have required a critical reassessment of its identity and operational strategies. To overcome

these challenges, the Levi Foundation launched a digitization process, implementing its internal digitalization laboratory - the LeviDigiLab - in 2023. By digitizing its extensive archival collection, the institution has not only safeguarded its historical assets but has also unlocked new research opportunities, fostering broader accessibility and engagement. By doing this, the Levi Foundation was also able to renew its identity, now capable of responding to contemporary needs.

This study is part of the broader research and dissemination FSE project 'Invisible Cultural Heritage. Enhancing New Digital Skills' ('Patrimoni culturali invisibili. Valorizzare le nuove competenze digitali'). The project, launched by the IUAV University of Venice, had a duration of 18 months, starting in February 2024 and concluding in July 2025. Its goal was to promote the development of skills related to digital innovation and to broaden public access to digital archives. Ca' Foscari University of Venice was invited as a minority partner to critically analyse the impact of digitalization within the Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation.

The data collection follows the principles of a single-case study research design [Yin09], being the Levi Foundation a revelatory case to inquire into how digitalization affects the organizational processes of heritage institutions. The data collected over 12 months of research comes from almost five hours of in-depth interviews with the institution's staff, analysis of materials provided by the Foundation, and observation and participation in more than ten cultural events organized by the Levi Foundation in collaboration with other institutions.

This investigation contributes to the broader discourse on heritage and identity construction within the Venetian cultural ecosystem, illustrating how digital strategies can reposition cultural institutions in response to contemporary pressures. The findings highlight that digital transformation is not merely a tool for preservation but a means of redefining organizational identity in an ever-evolving cultural landscape.

2. Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation: the evolution of a cultural identity in the Venetian ecosystem

The Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation is an internationally renowned cultural institution in the Venetian panorama that, since 1962, has been devoted to the study and dissemination of music and musicology. The origins of the Foundation are deeply rooted in the intellectual and cultural legacy of its founders, the couple Ugo Levi and Olga Brunner, whose lifelong commitment to music and culture shaped the institution's identity from its inception [Mil08]. Ugo Levi, a passionate music expert, amassed an extensive collection of musical manuscripts, scores, and archival material, which today constitute the core of today's Gianni Milner Library, one of the first private musical libraries [Mil03]. Between the Tens and Forties of the XX century [Zor94], together with his wife Olga Brunner, he transformed their residence at Palazzo Giustinian Lolin into a vibrant cultural salon, where they weekly [Bus13] hosted prominent and influential figures of the time, discussing music, art and culture, and developing cultural projects [Mil03]. This strong identity predated the formal establishment of the Levi Foundation, which, upon its founding in 1962, inherited not only a physical space but also a well-defined intellectual mission: to «increase and encourage the study of music» [Bru58] from all countries, all eras, and in all forms and styles [Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation]. The strategic location of Palazzo Giustinian Lolin, in proximity to other prestigious institutions such as the Benedetto Marcello Conservatory, La Fenice theatre, the Marciana Library, and the Luigi Nono Archive, further reinforced the Foundation's position within the dense network of cultural actors, allowing it to maintain a strong voice in the local landscape.

In its first decade, the cultural institution operated on the

renovation of some of its buildings, the acquisition of new materials and the organization of important conferences and seminars [Bus13]. A significant milestone in the Foundation's trajectory occurred in 1986 with the opening of the Gianni Milner Library, which made over 40.000 volumes and numerous personal collections accessible to scholars and professionals in the musicological field [Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation]. This move marked a shift towards greater public engagement, though the institution continued to primarily cater an academic and specialist audience. In 1992, the current president, Giorgio Busetto, assumed his presidency at the Levi Foundation, working on the economic sustainability of the institutions and developing a strategy which combines the valorisation of the past, the strengthening of the present, and a forward-looking vision for the future [Bus18].

Despite maintaining its core mission as a research hub throughout the XX century, the Levi Foundation, as many other cultural institutions, began facing significant challenges in the new millennium. As gathered from the interviews with the Foundation's personnel three main themes emerged: the economic sustainability, the internal organization structure, and the strategic importance of innovation. Currently, the main source of revenue comes from renting out its property spaces. However, such incomes are no longer sufficient to sustain the institution's cultural activities. Furthermore, this rental model has led to a progressive reduction of public access, limiting institution's visibility and engagement to the library space on the upper floor of the building, while most public events, concerts and seminars are hosted by other partners both in Venice and abroad. The situation is further exacerbated by a cultural offering that is strictly tailored to musicology scholars and students. This enables the Foundation to serve as a prestigious centre for those topics at an international level but also limits its audience to experts in the field and academics, reducing its appeal within a cultural landscape increasingly driven by diversification and innovation. Moreover, the staff highlighted critical issues related to the internal organizational structure, marked by loosely defined roles.

Over the past decade, these structural and strategic issues have eroded the Foundation's identity as a cultural hub, diminishing its role as an active site for interdisciplinary cultural production. In response, the Levi Foundation has embarked on a process of strategic repositioning, with digital innovation emerging as a key instrument for redefining its institutional identity. By leveraging digital transformation, the Foundation aims to «preserve and promote» its heritage and «expand its audience through access on a dedicated platform» - the LeviData [Cleinpress]. The personnel agree on the importance of digitisation as a strategic asset for institutional repositioning. As one staff member noted, digitisation is a fundamental tool for remaining competitive in today's cultural and local market. This shift reflects a broader trend among cultural institutions seeking to navigate the complexities of contemporary heritage management.

3. LeviDigiLab: digitalization as a tool for identity reconstruction

To reaffirm the Ugo and Olga Foundation as a strategic node within the Venetian cultural landscape - a role it had historically fulfilled during the early stages of its institutional development - the Foundation launched a comprehensive digital transformation process. The initiative materialized in the LeviDigiLab project, presented in 2022 under the Digital Culture Grant and fully operational in 2023, through a new digital laboratory, equipped with three custom-designed scanners – developed in collaboration with Made in Heritage network - and aligned with IIF standards [Cleinpress]. Nevertheless, the primary objective of the LeviDigiLab was to introduce and consolidate a «digital culture» [Cleinpress] within the Foundation, equipping it with the necessary

tools and competencies to digitally transform its heritage and organization. The project was conceived within a multidimensional framework, through which digitalization was not merely a tool for the long-term conservation of its heritage, but a lever to enhance its musical and cultural heritage and foster new opportunities for public engagement, via the LeviData platform, the digital interface through which the laboratory progressively disseminates its digitized content.

Although still in its early phase, the LeviDigiLab has already yielded observable outcomes in terms of operational, cultural, and social impact. Firstly, the implementation of the laboratory required significant organizational reconstructing, including the addition of three specialized professionals and the upskilling of the existing staff. This process involved a redefinition of the Foundation's operational structure and responsibility flows and was facilitated by a strong internal culture of collaboration, as stated by interviews with staff members. These testimonies highlight how digitization is not perceived merely as a technical necessity but a crucial step toward ensuring the Foundation's competitiveness in an increasingly digital and globalized cultural landscape. Secondly, the digital transformation is impacting the Foundation's cultural offering, which has expanded not only in content but also in form, becoming more accessible and engaging for a broader audience. The digitization process has initially triggered a systematic reorganization of archival materials, bringing to light previously forgotten narratives, now reactivated through new research pathways and forms of digital storytelling, including research project such as the IUAV's investigation into historical publisher stamps, offering new insights into the local history of Venice. These and other narratives are featured within the LeviData. As of today, the LeviData platform provides access to over 48.000 digital images, encompassing more than 2.000 digitized objects [Levi Foundation internal Report, December 2024]. The archive thus emerges as a hybrid entity which, thanks to its dual physical and digital nature, allows for the engagement of diverse audiences, and above all, enables the creation of new spaces for research opportunities - even beyond the fields of music and musicology. In fact, one of the most significant outcomes of this transformation is the recognition of digitization itself as a new domain of research and training for the Foundation, articulated through the development of conferences, seminars, and workshops addressed to professionals and experts in the field. Noteworthy is the conference series co-organized with Lyra srl and Made in Heritage, focused on the challenges and opportunities of cultural archive digitization.

Finally, the digitization of the Levi's archive has had a significant impact on its relationship with local institutions, contributing to the redefinition of its audience development strategies and reinforcing its role within the regional cultural ecosystem. In fact, between late 2024 and early 2025, the Levi Foundation was able to activate prominent projects with cultural and academic institutions, including the "Olivetti and Music" initiative in collaboration with the M9 Museum in Mestre which was capable of generating social value by «meeting the needs of a group of residents living near the museum, who had a strong interest in musical topics that would have otherwise gone unaddressed» [Pelinpress]. Another example is the Minor program Art Management, organized by Ca' Foscari University of Venice, where university students - guided by faculty members and professionals from the creative sector - were invited to explore the Levi Foundation and offer their personal interpretation of its identity through various expressive formats, including writing, video production, and performing arts. The project aimed to serve as an opportunity to reflect on the evolving identity of the Foundation, offering a fresh perspective from which to draw potential future opportunities. Moreover, thanks to "A ritmo di

Levi", the project's final event, the Foundation was able to present itself to the local audience and experiment with innovative forms of institutional storytelling.

Considering the above, it can be asserted that the digitization process has profoundly reconfigured both the organizational structure and the cultural programming of the Levi Foundation, strengthening the central role of the Gianni Milner Library. Moreover, through the activation of collaborative networks with local institutions, it has demonstrated the capacity to generate social value and to contribute meaningfully to the cultural development of its territory. The new collaborations initiated through the digital transformation, not only allow the Foundation to continue enriching its cultural heritage with new narratives but also become integral attributes of its continuously evolving organizational identity. This ongoing process enables stakeholders in the sector to recognize the Foundation for its research and educational activities, thereby strengthening its role within the contemporary cultural ecosystem.

4. Conclusions

The case of the Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation constitutes a paradigmatic example of how contemporary cultural institutions are increasingly configured as dynamic and transformative entities, capable of restructuring themselves in response to emerging societal demands and increasingly heterogeneous audiences. The ongoing digitization process, led by the LeviDigiLab project, demonstrates that digital innovation must be understood not merely as a tool for preservation but as a catalyst for broader institutional renewal. Specifically, our study contributes to the literature on digital heritage by showing that digitalization is not simply a technological force that might serve to address preservation or access issues [Eco15], but it also entails significant organizational challenges [TBB22]. What we add to this area of research is grasping how digital transformation may affect organizational identity in unintended ways. In fact, the findings underscore how the rediscovery of forgotten archival narratives, the activation of new forms of research engagement, and the expansion of the Foundation's audience beyond its traditional academic constituency have collectively contributed to a substantial reconfiguration of its organizational identity. This process has repositioned the Foundation within a dense network of local cultural actors. Its identity is thus not a fixed construct, but rather an evolving framework, continuously shaped by the emergence of new stories and collaborations - each instigated through the digital processing and dissemination of archival materials via the LeviData platform.

But what is now the Ugo and Olga Levi Foundation? Today, the Foundation presents itself as a site of institutional becoming, where its foundational mission - rooted in the promotion of music and musicology - intersects with contemporary discourses on digital transformation and cultural innovation. This transition marks a return to its original function as a cultural hub during the first half of the XX century, when the Foundation served as a nexus for intellectual and artistic exchange. Now, alongside musicians and scholars, a new constellation of actors - digital humanities, designers, data curators - participate in a more expansive and pluralistic institutional dialogue. While music remains central, it is entangled with emergent themes such as digital access, hybrid storytelling, and technological mediation. This result confirms the notion that any organizational identity is based upon the central, distinctive and durable features of an organization. However, our study sheds light also on the fact that digitalization offers opportunities for identity reconfiguration by exposing cultural organization to diverse audiences. It is thanks to this interplay between pressing societal transformations, changing groups of

stakeholders, and a commitment to its foundational mission that a cultural organization can sharply renew its identity while remaining anchored to its distinctive attributes. Looking forward, the intersection of cultural heritage and digital transformation raises critical questions regarding the evolving role of institutions within contemporary cultural ecosystems. Nonetheless, the digitisation process also presents limitations. Significant financial investments, ongoing technical maintenance, and the risk of marginalising non-digital audiences are challenges that require continued reflection and mitigation. By grounding the analysis in a detailed empirical case and integrating qualitative data from staff and event observation, the study offers insights into the digital transformation of mid-sized institutions, a relatively underexplored segment in Digital Humanities literature.

As the Levi Foundation continues to develop its hybrid institutional model, it actively contributes to broader scholarly and professional discourses on identity formation and strategic repositioning in the digital era. In doing so, it offers a compelling blueprint for cultural institutions seeking not only to preserve their legacy, but also to reimagine their identities, while overcoming market competitiveness and carving out their own - digital - space in which generate meaningful value for their audiences.

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